

The inter-fractional variation of the dose to the OARs and the hot spots near the three-channel gynecological applicators

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Abstract

The inter-fractional variation of the dose to the OARs of seven cervix cancer patients who received 4÷5 brachytherapy fractions with CT-MR compatible three-channel applicators (Elekta b.v.) was investigated with the conventional quantities and the dose to the hot spots with our alternative method.

Introduction

The CT-MR image-based HDR gynecological brachytherapy dosimetry protocols are based on the use of the quantities: the dose values of 2ccm volumes in the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid. Previously, we developed an alternative method to investigate the the hot spot doses at the OAR-s [1]. This study aimed to examine the inter-fractional variation of the dose to the OARs with the conventional D(2ccm) quantities and the dose to the hot spots with our method.

Material and Methods

Seven cervix cancer patients who received 4÷5 fractions of CT image-based brachytherapy treatments with three-channel gynecological applicators (Elekta b.v.) were considered. All insertions were performed with the same radiation oncologist and the organ contourings were also performed by him. We generated brachytherapy treatment plans with the Oncentra Brachy ver.4.5.4 (Elekta b.v.) brachytherapy planning system using manual graphical optimization. The objectives were: to achieve lower dose values to the 2ccm OAR volumes, than the prescription dose (5Gy). To investigate the dose fields near the CTV_HR, we generated the following structures: the extension of the CTV_HR by 5 mm in every direction (ctv05), the intersections of the structure ctv05 with the Bladder, Rectum, and the Sigmoid, referred to as *ib*, *ir*, and *is* respectively. These structures represent the volumes of the OARs' sections being near the CTV_HR, as illustrated in Fig.1. We obtained the recently accepted quantities from the DVH diagrams: the dose values to D(2ccm) as well as, the dose values of the 10% volumes in the structures *ib*, *ir*, and *is*, [1]. The DVH diagram of the brachytherapy plan of patient #1 fraction #1 is illustrated in Fig.2.

Fig.1. The intersection structures of patient #1, BT fraction #1 are: *ib* (upper), *ir* (middle), and *is* (lower image).

Results

Fig.2. DVH diagram of the patient #1, fraction #1

The $D(2\text{ccm})$ values of patient #1÷7, fractions #1÷5 for the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid are shown in Fig.3., while the $D(V10\%)$ values in Fig. 4. Fig. 5. and 6. show the averaged values for the 1÷5 fractions. The standard deviations of the $D(2\text{ccm})$ and $D(V10\%)$ varied between 0,2 and 2, the typical value was 1Gy.

Fig.3. The inter-fractional dose values of 2ccm volumes of the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid

Fig.4. The inter-fractional variation of the D(V10%) values of *ib*, *ir*, and *is* structures

Fig.5. The average of D(2ccm) values of the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid

Fig.6. The average dose values of D(V10%) of the intersection volumes *ib*, *ir*, and *is*

The brachytherapy plans approximated the objectives: the averaged dose values to 2ccm volumes in the Bladder, Rectum, and the Sigmoid were below 5 Gy, while the largest value was 6.2 Gy. The dose level in 10 % volumes of the intersection structures reached 8Gy, while the average dose varied between 3.5 and 6.2Gy. Missing data is shown in Fig.4. because there were no common volumes of the ctv05 and the Bladder, or Rectum or Sigmoid structures.

Discussion

In our previous study [2], in the eage of the biplane roentgen image-based applicator reconstruction, we inveastigated the insertion with metal Fletcher-Suit (FS) applicator. Depending on the patient anatomy and pathology and on the construction of the FS applicator, different geometrical arrangements in ovoid separation, in ovoids' sagittal level with respect to the tandem were experienced. The multiple insertions show minor differences in applicator geometries. The aim of the study was to evaluate the influence of main geometrical parameters, such as: the ovoid separation, symmetry and the ovoids' sagittal shift on dose distribution in different FS applicator arrangements. We tested the effect of dwell time settings in improvement of dose distribution of the less adequate insertions. We also investigated the effect of inter-fractional variation of the applicator geometry.

The recently used CT-MR compatible three-channel gynecological applicator's components are geometrically more fixed compared to the earlier ones. The inter-fractional variation of the dose fields are mainly due to the location of the applicator and due to the variation of the OARs' shape.

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References

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